

Uniform Order Eleven of Eight-Step Hybrid Block Backward Differentiation Formulae for the Solution of Stiff Ordinary Differential Equations

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ABSTRACT

In this research, we developed a uniform order eleven of eight step Second derivative hybrid block backward differentiation formula for integration of stiff systems in ordinary differential equations. The single continuous formulation developed is evaluated at some grid point of $x = x_{n+j}, j = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and 6 and its first derivative was also evaluated at off-grid point $x = x_{n+j}, j = \frac{15}{2}$ and grid point $x = x_{n+j}, j = 8$. The method is suitable for the solution of stiff ordinary differential equations and the accuracy and stability properties of the newly constructed method are investigated and are shown to be A-stable. Our numerical results obtained are compared with the theoretical solutions as well as ODE23 solver.

KEYWORDS: Backward Differentiation Formula, Second Derivative, off-step points, Stiff ODEs

1. INTRODUCTION

In sciences, researchers are not desired in all solutions to a differential equation, but only in those extra conditions satisfied solutions. For instance, in the case of Newton's second law of motion for a point particle, one could be actually interested only in solutions such that the particle that specifically position at some initial time. Such condition is called an initial condition.

A first order ordinary differential equations (ODEs) on the unknown y is

$$y'(t) = f(t, y(t)) \text{ and } y(t_0) = y_0 \quad a \leq t \leq b \quad (1)$$

where f is continuous within the interval of integration. is sufficiently differentiable and satisfies a Lipschitz condition (1).

Moreover, Awoyemi and Idowu (2005) derived a class of hybrid collocation methods for third-order ordinary differential equations. Hybrid block scheme were constructed to defeat the Dahlquist (1956) barrier theorem in accordance with the conventional linear multistep method was changed to include off-step points of derivation process (see Lambert (1973) and Gear (1965)).

Similarly, Researchers like Butcher (2003), Zarina *et al.* (2005), Awoyemi *et al.* (2007), Areyo *et al.* (2011), Ibijola *et al.* (2011) have all constructed linear multistep methods (LMMs) to generate numerical solution to (1).

Nasir *et al.* (2011), Zawawi *et al.* (2012), Akinfenwa *et al.* (2013), construct Block Backward Differentiation Formulas for Solving Ordinary Differential Equations. This

method possesses the requirement for stiffly stable and suitable to solve stiff problems. The numerical results were presented to verify the efficiency of this method as compared to the Classical Backward Differentiation Formula (BDF) method and ode15s in Matlab. The method outperformed the BDF method and ode15s in terms of maximum error and execution time.

2. CONSTRUCTION OF UNIFORM ORDER ELEVEN OF EIGHT-STEP HYBRID

In this research, we constructed eight-step hybrid block backward differentiation formula. The method will be applied in block form by Onumanyi *et al* (1994,1999) where $k - step$ multistep collocation method with t interpolation points and m collocation points were obtained as follows:

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} \alpha_j(x)y_{n+j} + h \sum_{j=0}^{s-1} \beta_j(x)f_{n+j} \tag{2}$$

and its extension it to the second derivative gives the general form of the continuous $k - step$ 2^{nd} derivative linear multistep method as:

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} \alpha_j(x)y_{n+j} + h \sum_{j=0}^{s-1} \beta_j(x)f_{n+j} + h^2 \sum_{j=0}^{t-1} \gamma_j(x)g_{n+j} \tag{3}$$

Here the coefficients $\alpha_j(x)$, $\beta_j(x)$ and $\gamma_j(x)$ are polynomials of degree $(p - 1)$.

where

$$\alpha_j(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{r+s+t-1} \alpha_{j,i+1}x^i \tag{4}$$

$$h\beta_j(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{r+s+t-1} h\beta_{j,i+1}x^i \tag{5}$$

$$h^2\beta_j(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{r+s+t-1} h^2\gamma_{j,i+1}x^i \tag{6}$$

2.1. Specification of the Hybrid Block Methods

From equation (2) - (6) we propose continuous k -step of extended block hybrid backward differentiation formula of the form

$$y(x) = \sum_j^k \alpha_j(x)y_{n+j} + h\beta_{k-1}(x)f_{n+k-1} + h\frac{\beta_{2k-1}}{2}f_{n+\frac{2k-1}{2}} + h\beta_k(x)f_{n+k} + h^2\gamma_{k-1}(x)g_{n+k-1} + h^2\gamma_k(x)g_{n+k} \tag{7}$$

2.1.2 Eight Step Method with One Off-Step Point

In this case $= 8$, $S = 8$, $t = 8$ and (7) becomes

$$y(x) = \alpha_0(x)y_n + \alpha_1(x)y_{n+1} + \alpha_2(x)y_{n+2} + \alpha_3(x)y_{n+3} + \alpha_4(x)y_{n+4} + \alpha_5(x)y_{n+5} + \alpha_6(x)f_{n+6} + \alpha_7(x)y_{n+7} = h[\beta_0(x)f_n + \beta_1(x)f_{n+1} + \beta_2(x)f_{n+2} + \beta_3(x)f_{n+3} + \beta_4(x)f_{n+4} + \beta_5(x)f_{n+5} + \beta_6(x)f_{n+6} + \beta_7(x)f_{n+7} + \beta_{\frac{15}{2}}(x)f_{n+\frac{15}{2}} + \beta_8(x)f_{n+8}] + h^2[\gamma_0(x)g_n + \gamma_1(x)g_{n+1} + \gamma_2(x)g_{n+2} + \gamma_3(x)g_{n+3} + \gamma_4(x)g_{n+4} + \gamma_5(x)g_{n+5} + \gamma_6(x)g_{n+6} + \gamma_7(x)g_{n+7} + \gamma_8(x)g_{n+8}] \tag{8}$$

and interpolating (4) at $x = x_n, x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}, x_{n+3}, x_{n+4}, x_{n+5}, x_{n+6}, x_{n+7}$ and collocating (5) at $x = x_{n+7}, x_{n+\frac{15}{2}}, x_{n+8}$ to give the systems of equation.

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=0}^6 a_j x^j = y_n \tag{9}$$

$$y'(x) = \sum_{j=1}^6 j a_j x^{j-1} = f_{n+j} \tag{10}$$

$$y''(x) = \sum_{j=2}^6 j(j-1) a_j x^{j-2} = f_{n+j} \tag{11}$$

Expressing the system of equations (9) -(11) in the form $AX = Y$ as:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_n & x_n^2 & x_n^3 & x_n^4 & x_n^5 & x_n^6 & x_n^7 & x_n^8 & x_n^9 & x_n^{10} & x_n^{11} & x_n^{12} \\ 1 & x_{n+1} & x_{n+1}^2 & x_{n+1}^3 & x_{n+1}^4 & x_{n+1}^5 & x_{n+1}^6 & x_{n+1}^7 & x_{n+1}^8 & x_{n+1}^9 & x_{n+1}^{10} & x_{n+1}^{11} & x_{n+1}^{12} \\ 1 & x_{n+2} & x_{n+2}^2 & x_{n+2}^3 & x_{n+2}^4 & x_{n+2}^5 & x_{n+2}^6 & x_{n+2}^7 & x_{n+2}^8 & x_{n+2}^9 & x_{n+2}^{10} & x_{n+2}^{11} & x_{n+2}^{12} \\ 1 & x_{n+3} & x_{n+3}^2 & x_{n+3}^3 & x_{n+3}^4 & x_{n+3}^5 & x_{n+3}^6 & x_{n+3}^7 & x_{n+3}^8 & x_{n+3}^9 & x_{n+3}^{10} & x_{n+3}^{11} & x_{n+3}^{12} \\ 1 & x_{n+4} & x_{n+4}^2 & x_{n+4}^3 & x_{n+4}^4 & x_{n+4}^5 & x_{n+4}^6 & x_{n+4}^7 & x_{n+4}^8 & x_{n+4}^9 & x_{n+4}^{10} & x_{n+4}^{11} & x_{n+4}^{12} \\ 1 & x_{n+5} & x_{n+5}^2 & x_{n+5}^3 & x_{n+5}^4 & x_{n+5}^5 & x_{n+5}^6 & x_{n+5}^7 & x_{n+5}^8 & x_{n+5}^9 & x_{n+5}^{10} & x_{n+5}^{11} & x_{n+5}^{12} \\ 1 & x_{n+6} & x_{n+6}^2 & x_{n+6}^3 & x_{n+6}^4 & x_{n+6}^5 & x_{n+6}^6 & x_{n+6}^7 & x_{n+6}^8 & x_{n+6}^9 & x_{n+6}^{10} & x_{n+6}^{11} & x_{n+6}^{12} \\ 1 & x_{n+7} & x_{n+7}^2 & x_{n+7}^3 & x_{n+7}^4 & x_{n+7}^5 & x_{n+7}^6 & x_{n+7}^7 & x_{n+7}^8 & x_{n+7}^9 & x_{n+7}^{10} & x_{n+7}^{11} & x_{n+7}^{12} \\ 0 & 1 & 2x_{n+7} & 3x_{n+7}^2 & 4x_{n+7}^3 & 5x_{n+7}^4 & 6x_{n+7}^5 & 7x_{n+7}^6 & 8x_{n+7}^7 & 9x_{n+7}^8 & 10x_{n+7}^9 & 11x_{n+7}^{10} & 12x_{n+7}^{11} \\ 0 & 1 & 2x_{n+\frac{15}{2}} & 3x_{n+\frac{15}{2}}^2 & 4x_{n+\frac{15}{2}}^3 & 5x_{n+\frac{15}{2}}^4 & 6x_{n+\frac{15}{2}}^5 & 7x_{n+\frac{15}{2}}^6 & 8x_{n+\frac{15}{2}}^7 & 9x_{n+\frac{15}{2}}^8 & 10x_{n+\frac{15}{2}}^9 & 11x_{n+\frac{15}{2}}^{10} & 12x_{n+\frac{15}{2}}^{11} \\ 0 & 1 & 2x_{n+8} & 3x_{n+8}^2 & 4x_{n+8}^3 & 5x_{n+8}^4 & 6x_{n+8}^5 & 7x_{n+8}^6 & 8x_{n+8}^7 & 9x_{n+8}^8 & 10x_{n+8}^9 & 11x_{n+8}^{10} & 12x_{n+8}^{11} \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+7} & 12x_{n+7}^2 & 15x_{n+7}^3 & 30x_{n+7}^4 & 42x_{n+7}^5 & 56x_{n+7}^6 & 72x_{n+7}^7 & 90x_{n+7}^8 & 110x_{n+7}^9 & 132x_{n+7}^{10} \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+8} & 12x_{n+8}^2 & 15x_{n+8}^3 & 30x_{n+8}^4 & 42x_{n+8}^5 & 56x_{n+8}^6 & 72x_{n+8}^7 & 90x_{n+8}^8 & 110x_{n+8}^9 & 132x_{n+8}^{10} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \\ a_4 \\ a_5 \\ a_6 \\ a_7 \\ a_8 \\ a_9 \\ a_{10} \\ a_{11} \\ a_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} y_n \\ y_{n+1} \\ y_{n+2} \\ y_{n+3} \\ y_{n+4} \\ y_{n+5} \\ y_{n+6} \\ y_{n+7} \\ f_{n+7} \\ f_{n+\frac{15}{2}} \\ f_{n+8} \\ g_{n+7} \\ g_{n+8} \end{bmatrix} \tag{12}$$

Using Maple software and inverting the matrix in (12) is yields the elements of the matrix A^{-1} .

The columns of A^{-1} give the continuous coefficients of (4)-(6) as:

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$$\alpha_0(x) = 1 - \frac{95958313819129x}{29479449569430h} + \frac{111379502927091629x^2}{24762737638321200h^2} - \frac{14752082604856619623x^3}{4160139923237961600h^3} + \frac{5978817275676899711x^4}{3328111938590369280h^4} - \frac{607983743988885997x^5}{978856452526579200h^5} \\ + \frac{10064346687661109357x^6}{66562238771807385600h^6} - \frac{8316257821028201x^7}{316963041770511360h^7} + \frac{10247925246994591x^8}{3169630417705113600h^8} - \frac{1151437056841919x^9}{4160139923237961600h^9} \\ + \frac{1042639590961571x^{10}}{66562238771807385600h^{10}} - \frac{17550288818501x^{11}}{33281119385903692800h^{11}} + \frac{31325547497x^{12}}{3915425810106316800h^{12}}$$

$$\alpha_1(x) = \frac{5999869653050x}{421134993849h} - \frac{162362039569331x^2}{5053619926188h^2} + \frac{19376892463308499x^3}{606434391142560h^3} - \frac{135118095989390719x^4}{7277212693710720h^4} + \frac{1002553554614321x^5}{142690444974720h^5} - \frac{53054436242457737x^6}{29108850774842880h^6} \\ + \frac{11911219801561x^7}{35936852808448h^7} - \frac{82149948379561x^8}{1940590051656192h^8} + \frac{4520601070249x^9}{1212868782285120h^9} - \frac{6280178983223x^{10}}{29108850774842880h^{10}} + \frac{35892089683x^{11}}{4851475129140480h^{11}} \\ - \frac{195148837x^{12}}{1712285339696640h^{12}}$$

$$\alpha_2(x) = -\frac{6875640670346x}{140378331283h} + \frac{5682835861917011x^2}{42113499384900h^2} - \frac{77232977678555219x^3}{5053619926188000h^3} + \frac{5898372469497008023x^4}{60643439114256000h^4} - \frac{140381714892468973x^5}{3567261124368000h^5} + \frac{2606002022753332429x^6}{242573756457024000h^6} \\ - \frac{3288459697500179x^7}{1617158376380160h^7} + \frac{289136258920171x^8}{1078105584253440h^8} - \frac{122500746419197x^9}{5053619926188000h^9} + \frac{347843988763331x^{10}}{242573756457024000h^{10}} - \frac{6073810272629x^{11}}{121286878228512000h^{11}} \\ + \frac{11180057209x^{12}}{14269044497472000h^{12}}$$

$$\alpha_3(x) = \frac{124156819047625x}{842269987698h} - \frac{8705963111552455x^2}{20214479704752h^2} + \frac{84000083720233513x^3}{161715837638016h^3} - \frac{75366803439211717x^4}{215621116850688h^4} + \frac{5641881259818595x^5}{38050785326592h^5} - \frac{108983688887548537x^6}{2587453402208256h^6} \\ + \frac{3555263960924639x^7}{431242233701376h^7} - \frac{2894393499959887x^8}{2587453402208256h^8} + \frac{33503499322231x^9}{324331675276032h^9} - \frac{5396554991149x^{10}}{862484467402752h^{10}} + \frac{287842984985x^{11}}{1293726701104128h^{11}} \\ - \frac{538239565x^{12}}{152203141306368h^{12}}$$

$$\alpha_4(x) = -\frac{324847870920125x}{842269987698h} + \frac{23427907792376395x^2}{20214479704752h^2} - \frac{70097644067670879x^3}{485147512914048h^3} + \frac{5858213737831411585x^4}{5821770154968576h^4} - \frac{50360748668263645x^5}{114152355979776h^5} + \frac{3008740914626408279x^6}{23287080619874304h^6} \\ - \frac{33633230900175019x^7}{1293726701104128h^7} + \frac{28069177569117659x^8}{7762360206624768h^8} - \frac{166103439749567x^9}{485147512914048h^9} + \frac{491256957909977x^{10}}{23287080619874304h^{10}} - \frac{2963717454581x^{11}}{3881180103312384h^{11}} \\ + \frac{16893432587x^{12}}{1369828271757312h^{12}}$$

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$$\alpha_5(x) = \frac{698233548697762x}{701891656415h} - \frac{127982190512855483x^2}{42113499348900h^2} + \frac{3907504681261828703x^3}{1010723985237600h^3} - \frac{6679512172825498303x^4}{2425737564570240h^4} + \frac{881694260693648351x^5}{713452224873600h^5}$$

$$- \frac{17972507404872403181x^6}{48514751291404800h^6} + \frac{123294391180745231x^7}{1617158376380160h^7} - \frac{58404991154460107x^8}{5390527921267200h^8} + \frac{2115964283425693x^9}{2021447970475200h^9}$$

$$- \frac{3188461778077843x^{10}}{48514751291404800h^{10}} + \frac{58725123939133x^{11}}{24257375645702400h^{11}} - \frac{x}{2853808899494400h^{12}}$$

$$\alpha_6(x) = -\frac{1591448100803050x}{421134993849h} + \frac{58973616807690011x^2}{5053619926188h^2} - \frac{9125523287132968219x^3}{606434391142560h^3} + \frac{26407945574782487893x^4}{2425737564570240h^4} - \frac{709173203422711231x^5}{142690444974720h^5}$$

$$+ \frac{14717766075275137199x^6}{9702950258280960h^6} - \frac{102837002696707733x^7}{323431675276032h^7} + \frac{3307845701319711x^8}{71873705616896h^8} - \frac{2745685566667217x^9}{606434391142560h^9}$$

$$+ \frac{280733838723136x^{10}}{9702950258280960h^{10}} - \frac{52594481758343x^{11}}{4851475129140480h^{11}} + \frac{103239426419x^{12}}{570761779898880h^{12}}$$

$$\alpha_7(x) = \frac{18043919361064657x}{5895889913886h} - \frac{234408889565975928593x^2}{24762737638321200h^2} + \frac{254426896842248963872279x^3}{20800699616189808000h^3} - \frac{2214071776927267887465043x^4}{249608395394277696000h^4} + \frac{2207889379530816131509x^5}{543809140292544000h^5}$$

$$- \frac{1240587114881513356098389x^6}{998433581577110784000h^6} + \frac{82789381930492078319x^7}{316963041770511360h^7} - \frac{72105563826067360439x^8}{1901778250623068160h^8} + \frac{155606351177055440329x^9}{41601399232379616000h^9}$$

$$- \frac{239203987064516185771x^{10}}{998433581577110784000h^{10}} + \frac{499457292157396621x^{11}}{55468532309839488000h^{11}} - \frac{8845925643617369x^{12}}{58731387151594752000h^{12}}$$

$$\beta_7(x) = -\frac{30797607491730x}{140378331283} + \frac{12252449651037159x^2}{19652966379620h} - \frac{3924857667428473659x^3}{5502830586293600h^2} + \frac{28805166480229703303x^4}{66033967035523200h^3} - \frac{1824665680566703409x^5}{11653053006268800h^4}$$

$$+ \frac{26167954478105592707x^6}{792407604426278400h^5} - \frac{2623989574274443x^7}{754673908977408h^6} + \frac{64286272312943x^8}{1509347817954816h^7} - \frac{2052021323393473x^9}{33016983517761600h^8} + \frac{697442591071403x^{10}}{88045289380697600h^9}$$

$$- \frac{179476384395293x^{11}}{396203802213139200h^{10}} + \frac{479316757153x^{12}}{46612212025075200h^{11}}$$

$$\beta_{15/2}(x) = -\frac{428190539055104x}{140378331283} + \frac{6685811626819584x^2}{701891656415h} - \frac{78708148640651264x^3}{6317024907735h^2} + \frac{11583149024190976x^4}{1263404981547h^3} - \frac{1585503861215744x^5}{371589700455h^4} + \frac{8402119605809536x^6}{6317024907735h^5}$$

$$- \frac{120118667889920x^7}{421134993849h^6} + \frac{89048602174336x^8}{2105674969245h^7} - \frac{26946704038912x^9}{6317024907735h^8} + \frac{1766885496448x^{10}}{63170249907735h^9} - \frac{67963410176x^{11}}{6317024907735h^{10}}$$

$$+ \frac{68496256x^{12}}{371589700455h^{11}}$$

$$\beta_8(x) = \frac{102709446821625x}{140378331283} - \frac{1285663550076535x^2}{561513325132h} + \frac{40470004012999603x^3}{13476319803168h^2} - \frac{358511358722606365x^4}{1617158337638016h^3} + \frac{9851655119649403x^5}{9512696331648h^4} - \frac{209718963335245531x^6}{646863350552064h^5}$$

$$+ \frac{7530890237766749x^7}{107810558425344h^6} - \frac{748235136449605x^8}{71873705616896h^7} + \frac{14230248199867x^9}{13476319803168h^8} - \frac{45054856385429x^{10}}{646863350552064h^9} + \frac{872012211011x^{11}}{323431675276032h^{10}}$$

$$- \frac{1769443135x^{12}}{38050785326592h^{11}}$$

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$$\gamma_7(x) = \frac{252474550097700xh}{140378331283} - \frac{1570774572740333}{280756662566} x^2 + \frac{1717354357900665499x^3}{235835596555440h} - \frac{15074283296663869543x^4}{2830027158665280h^2} + \frac{45540634791210947x^5}{18496909533760h^3}$$

$$- \frac{8622045232427895329x^6}{11320108634661120h^4} + \frac{2910438299459199x^7}{17968426404224h^5} - \frac{2565992829113863x^8}{107810558425344h^6} + \frac{1121624842813669x^9}{471671193110880h^7} - \frac{1747468970243231x^{10}}{11320108634661120h^8}$$

$$+ \frac{3695515319961x^{11}}{628894924147840h^9} - \frac{66323138549x^{12}}{665888743215360h^{10}}$$

$$\gamma_8(x) = -\frac{16888540189500xh}{140378331283} + \frac{52898108169060}{140378331283} x^2 - \frac{1111375015828707x^3}{2246053300528h} - \frac{3286416400864111x^4}{8984213202112h^2} + \frac{904578847981169x^5}{528483129536h^3} - \frac{1929273942531457x^6}{35936852808448h^4}$$

$$+ \frac{208278204400469x^7}{17968426404224h^5} - \frac{62226870194839x^8}{35936852808448h^6} + \frac{395507042623x^9}{2246053300528h^7} - \frac{418590251343x^{10}}{35936852808448h^8} + \frac{8126500505x^{11}}{17968426404224h^9} - \frac{16544781x^{12}}{2113932518144h^{10}}$$

Evaluating (8) at the following points at

$x_n, x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}, x_{n+3}, x_{n+4}, x_{n+5}, x_{n+6}, x_{n+15/3}$ and x_{n+8} yields the following discrete methods which constitute the new eight step block method.

$$y_n - \frac{795573993889721900}{111379502927091629} y_{n+1} + \frac{3341507486807202468}{111379502927091629} y_{n+2} - \frac{10664804811651757375}{111379502927091629} y_{n+3} + \frac{28699187045661083875}{111379502927091629} y_{n+4} - \frac{75253528021559024004}{111379502927091629} y_{n+5}$$

$$+ \frac{288970722357681053900}{111379502927091629} y_{n+6} - \frac{234408889565975928593}{111379502927091629} y_{n+7}$$

$$= \frac{1260h}{111379502927091629} \left[12252449651037159f_{n+7} + 187202725550948352f_{n+\frac{15}{2}} - 44998224252678725f_{n+8} \right] + \frac{88200h^2}{111379502927091629} [140378331283g_n$$

$$+ 1570774572740333g_{n+7} - 105796216338120g_{n+8}]$$

$$y_n + \frac{25231414254947640}{4965391873495939} y_{n+1} - \frac{918591857070157676}{24826959367479695} y_{n+2} + \frac{585503967350684025}{4965391873495939} y_{n+3} - \frac{4482510795788159225}{14896175620487817} y_{n+4} + \frac{3773303822956282636}{4965391873495939} y_{n+5}$$

$$- \frac{14112172589850215860}{4965391873495939} y_{n+6} + \frac{171015849451373356153}{74480878102439085} y_{n+7}$$

$$= \frac{28h}{4965391873495939} \left[32832731120396717f_{n+7} + 399847878563266560f_{n+\frac{15}{2}} - 95591127585482025f_{n+8} \right] + \frac{1960h^2}{4965391873495939} [5615133251320g_{n+1}$$

$$- 3388606915725319g_{n+7} + 224219376062145g_{n+8}]$$

$$y_n - \frac{7222751481023540}{206294902600341} y_{n+1} + \frac{8110158627648812}{5157372565008525} y_{n+2} + \frac{19088416297961325}{68764967533447} y_{n+3} - \frac{172698241297211525}{206294902600341} y_{n+4} + \frac{423413680921142884}{206294902600341} y_{n+5}$$

$$- \frac{512403409953341620}{68764967533447} y_{n+6} + \frac{30898039789388169313}{5157372565008525} y_{n+7}$$

$$= \frac{28h}{343824837667235} \left[7185554611961157f_{n+7} + 70180046374502400f_{n+\frac{15}{2}} - 16669945678353625f_{n+8} \right] - \frac{392h^2}{68764967533447} [7861186551848g_{n+2}$$

$$+ 601842327156471g_{n+7} - 38993163236825g_{n+8}]$$

“Uniform Order Eleven of Eight-Step Hybrid Block Backward Differentiation Formulae for the Solution of Stiff Ordinary Differential Equations”

$$\begin{aligned}
 & y_n - \frac{2070320941916780}{88165482138851} y_{n+1} + \frac{180752455135885332}{440827410694255} y_{n+2} - \frac{41538978652452925}{88165482138851} y_{n+3} - \frac{85609840632881075}{88165482138851} y_{n+4} + \frac{333063784390344924}{88165482138851} y_{n+5} \\
 & \quad - \frac{1210325056048167220}{88165482138851} y_{n+6} + \frac{4851208776878785793}{440827410694255} y_{n+7} \\
 & = \frac{252h}{88165482138851} \left[440062565156559 f_{n+7} + 3569446989660160 f_{n+\frac{15}{2}} - 841909412290625 f_{n+8} \right] + \frac{17640h^2}{88165482138851} [1965296637962 g_{n+3} \\
 & \quad - 30992386067543 g_{n+7} + 1963324978713 g_{n+8}] \\
 & y_n - \frac{535551344432860}{26631670316133} y_{n+1} + \frac{10225338751074412}{44386117193555} y_{n+2} - \frac{827110478267325}{306111153059} y_{n+3} + \frac{1210127800927725}{306111153059} y_{n+4} + \frac{21449184720713764}{8877223438711} y_{n+5} - \frac{190583150657241580}{8877223438711} y_{n+6} \\
 & \quad + \frac{2342265532264503639}{133158351580665} y_{n+7} \\
 & = \frac{28h}{8877223438711} \left[667521725849171 f_{n+7} + 5151530052157440 f_{n+\frac{15}{2}} - 1207191039323325 f_{n+8} \right] - \frac{1960h^2}{8877223438711} [9826483189810 g_{n+4} \\
 & \quad + 45078599072657 g_{n+7} - 2806256440575 g_{n+8}] \\
 & y_n - \frac{28732889416700}{1558701718659} y_{n+1} + \frac{14647518007276}{82036932561} y_{n+2} - \frac{231791360980375}{173189079851} y_{n+3} + \frac{18773267530814125}{1558701718659} y_{n+4} - \frac{3928035699532}{219938157} y_{n+5} - \frac{3126320160999700}{173189079851} y_{n+6} \\
 & \quad + \frac{39036596515149631}{1558701718659} y_{n+7} \\
 & = \frac{140h}{519567239553} \left[7012323610059 f_{n+7} + 98186615783424 f_{n+\frac{15}{2}} - 22800086843975 f_{n+8} \right] + \frac{9800h^2}{519567239553} [462422738344 g_{n+5} - 855181579233 g_{n+7} \\
 & \quad + 52722651695 g_{n+8}] \\
 & y_n - \frac{393848612015180}{22694743922483} y_{n+1} + \frac{17002139804752068}{113473719612415} y_{n+2} - \frac{21584615528729575}{22694743922483} y_{n+3} + \frac{120848531925713725}{22694743922483} y_{n+4} - \frac{931785054474996708}{22694743922483} y_{n+5} \\
 & \quad + \frac{669436923774516380}{22694743922483} y_{n+6} + \frac{799974701053192307}{113473719612415} y_{n+7} \\
 & \quad - \frac{252h}{22694743922483} \left[415729917509259 f_{n+7} - 5120456609300480 f_{n+\frac{15}{2}} + 1122075341897825 f_{n+8} \right] - \frac{17640h^2}{22694743922483} [39305932759240 g_{n+6} \\
 & \quad + 47323702151687 g_{n+7} - 256515380385 g_{n+8}] \\
 & y_{n+\frac{15}{2}} + \frac{1385420343021}{8243051549790568448} y_n - \frac{1816784820775}{294394698206806016} y_{n+1} + \frac{6675149415753}{294394698206806016} y_{n+2} - \frac{148545520998875}{1177578792827224064} y_{n+3} + \frac{675021185821125}{1177578792827224064} y_{n+4} \\
 & \quad - \frac{779956749745173}{294394698206806016} y_{n+5} + \frac{6268503501535275}{294394698206806016} y_{n+6} - \frac{8400581608123449459}{8243051549790568448} y_{n+7} \\
 & = \frac{6435h}{294394698206806016} \left[14072591027781 f_{n+7} + 8522418946048 f_{n+\frac{15}{2}} - 512303316525 f_{n+8} \right] + \frac{289864575h^2}{147197349103403008} [24728719 g_{n+7} + 768915 g_{n+8}] \\
 & y_{n+8} - \frac{40335}{140378331283} y_n + \frac{654800}{140378331283} y_{n+1} - \frac{5230064}{140378331283} y_{n+2} + \frac{281410092}{140378331283} y_{n+3} - \frac{121250500}{140378331283} y_{n+4} + \frac{507886960}{140378331283} y_{n+5} - \frac{3191134800}{140378331283} y_{n+6} - \frac{137597358436}{140378331283} y_{n+7} = \\
 & \frac{2520h}{140378331283} \left[12281666 f_{n+7} + 32112640 f_{n+\frac{15}{2}} + 12283227 f_{n+8} \right] - \frac{352800h^2}{140378331283} [491 g_{n+7} + 5692 g_{n+8}] \tag{13}
 \end{aligned}$$

3. CONVERGENCE AND STABILITY ANALYSIS OF THE METHOD

In this section the analysis of the newly constructed methods is carried by analyzing the order, error constant consistency, convergence and plotting the regions of absolute stability.

The new method in equation (3) is expressed in the form:

$$\sum_{j=0}^k (\alpha_j y_{n+j} - h\beta_j f_{n+j} - h^2 \lambda_j f'_{n+j}) = 0 \tag{14}$$

Which is written symbolically as:

$$\rho(E)y_n - h^2 \sigma(E) = 0 \tag{15}$$

E being the shift operator and is defined as $E^i y_n = y_{n+i}$, $\rho(E)$ and $\sigma(E)$ are respectively the first and second characteristics polynomial of the LMM such that

$$\rho(E) = \sum_{j=0}^k \alpha_j E^j, \quad \sigma(E) = \sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j E^j \tag{16}$$

Following (Fatunla, 1991) and (Lambert,1973) we defined the local truncation error associated with (3) to be linear difference operator

$$[y(x); h] = \sum_{j=0}^k \alpha_j y_{n+j} - h\beta_k f_{n+k} - h^2 \gamma_k g_{n+k} \tag{17}$$

Assuming that $y(x)$ is sufficiently differentiable, we can we expand the terms in (17) as a Taylor series and comparing the coefficients of h gives

$$L[y(x); h] = c_0 y(x) + c_1 h y'(x) + c_2 h^2 y''(x) + \dots + c_p h^p y^{(p)}(x) + \dots \tag{18}$$

Where the constants $C_p, p = 0, 1, 2, \dots, j = 1, 2, \dots, k$.

Using the concept above, the hybrid block method are obtained with the help of MAPLE 18 SOFTWARE have the following uniform order and error constants.

3.1 Table 1 Order and Error Constants of the Eight -Step

y_n	11	$\frac{11097820685016920015}{764508908091556941456}$
y_{n+1}	11	$-\frac{1412674980352712279}{102247349459028375888}$
y_{n+2}	11	$-\frac{14601896648447213}{472002737149580208}$
y_{n+3}	11	$-\frac{29213909016714541}{605167869401073264}$
y_{n+4}	11	$-\frac{12085140283692917}{182799785049936912}$
y_{n+5}	11	$-\frac{922206057457405}{10698928596875376}$
y_{n+6}	11	$-\frac{1575458937383051}{14161520207629392}$
$y_{n+\frac{15}{2}}$	11	$-\frac{463663785585}{18841260685235585024}$
y_{n+8}	11	$\frac{11276615}{240889216481628}$

3.2 Zero Stability of the Eight -Step Method

The zero stability of the eight-step new method is determined using the approach of Ehigie *et al.* (2014) in which Maple18 software was used to yields the stability polynomial of the method as

$$\rho(r) = \det(rA - B)$$

(19)

=det r	795573993889721900	3341507486807202468	10664804811651757375	282699187045661083875	-75253528021559024004	288970722357681053900	2344088895659759289593	0	0	
	111379502927091629	111379502927091629	111379502927091629	111379502927091629	111379502927091629	111379502927091629	111379502927091629	111379502927091629	0	0
	25231414254947460	-918591857070157676	585503967350684025	-4482510795788159225	3773303822956282636	-14112172589850215860	171015849451373356153	171015849451373356153	0	0
	4965391873495939	24826959367479695	4965391873495939	14896175620487817	4965391873495939	4965391873495939	74480878102439085	74480878102439085	0	0
	-7222751481023540	8110158627648812	19088416297961325	-172698241297211525	423413680921142884	-512403409953341620	30898039789388169313	30898039789388169313	0	0
	206294902600341	5157372565008525	68764967533447	206294902600341	206294902600341	68764967533447	5157372565008525	5157372565008525	0	0
	-2070320941916780	180752455135885332	-41538978652452925	85609840632881075	333063784390344924	-1210325056048167220	4851208776878785793	4851208776878785793	0	0
	88165482138851	440827410694255	88165482138851	88165482138851	88165482138851	88165482138851	440827410694255	440827410694255	0	0
	535551344432860	10225338751074412	827110478267325	1210127809027725	21449184720713764	-190583150657241580	2342265532284503639	2342265532284503639	0	0
	26631670316133	44386117193555	306111153059	306111153059	8877223438711	306111153059	133158351580665	133158351580665	0	0
	-28732889416700	14647518007276	-231791360980375	18773267530814125	3928035699532	-3126320160999700	39036596515149631	39036596515149631	0	0
	1558701718659	82036932561	173189079851	1558701718659	219938157	173189079851	1558701718659	1558701718659	0	0
	-393848612015180	17302139804752068	-21584615528729575	120848531925713725	-931785054474996708	669436923774516380	799974701053192307	799974701053192307	0	0
	22694743922483	113473719612415	22694743922483	22694743922483	22694743922483	22694743922483	113473719612415	113473719612415	0	0
	816784820775	6675149415753	-148545520998875	675021185821125	-779956749745173	6268503501535275	8400581608123449459	8400581608123449459	1	0
	294394698206806016	294394698206806016	1177578792827224064	1177578792827224064	294394698206806016	294394698206806016	8243051549790568448	8243051549790568448	1	0
654800	-5230064	28141092	-121250500	507886960	-3191134800	-137597358436	-137597358436	0	1	
140378331283	140378331283	140378331283	140378331283	140378331283	140378331283	140378331283	140378331283	0	1	

0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1385420343021
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8243051549790568448
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	40335
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	140378331283

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$$= \det \begin{bmatrix} \frac{795573993889721900}{111379502927091629} & \frac{3341507486807202468}{111379502927091629} & \frac{10664804811651757375}{111379502927091629} & \frac{282699187045661083875}{111379502927091629} & \frac{-75253528021559024004}{111379502927091629} & \frac{288970722357681053900}{111379502927091629} & \frac{2344088895659759289593}{111379502927091629} & 0 & 1 \\ \frac{25231414254947460}{4965391873495939} & \frac{-918591857070157676}{24826959367479695} & \frac{585503967350684025}{4965391873495939} & \frac{-4482510795788159225}{14896175620487817} & \frac{3773303822956282636}{4965391873495939} & \frac{-14112172589850215860}{4965391873495939} & \frac{171015849451373356153}{74480878102439085} & 0 & 1 \\ \frac{-7222751481023540}{206294902600341} & \frac{8110158627648812}{5157372565008525} & \frac{19088416297961325}{68764967533447} & \frac{-172698241297211525}{206294902600341} & \frac{423413680921142884}{206294902600341} & \frac{-512403409953341620}{68764967533447} & \frac{30898039789388169313}{5157372565008525} & 0 & 1 \\ \frac{-2070320941916780}{88165482138851} & \frac{180752455135885332}{440827410694255} & \frac{-41538978652452925}{88165482138851} & \frac{85609840632881075}{88165482138851} & \frac{333063784390344924}{88165482138851} & \frac{-1210325056048167220}{88165482138851} & \frac{4851208776878785793}{440827410694255} & 0 & 1 \\ \frac{535551344432860}{26631670316133} & \frac{10225338751074412}{44386117193555} & \frac{827110478267325}{306111153059} & \frac{827110478267325}{306111153059} & \frac{1210127809027725}{306111153059} & \frac{21449184720713764}{8877223438711} & \frac{2342265532284503639}{133158351580665} & 0 & 1 \\ \frac{-28732889416700}{1558701718659} & \frac{14647518007276}{82036932561} & \frac{-231791360980375}{173189079851} & \frac{-231791360980375}{173189079851} & \frac{18773267530814125}{1558701718659} & \frac{3928035699532}{219938157} & \frac{39036596515149631}{1558701718659} & 0 & 1 \\ \frac{-393848612015180}{22694743922483} & \frac{17302139804752068}{113473719612415} & \frac{-21584615528729575}{22694743922483} & \frac{-21584615528729575}{22694743922483} & \frac{120848531925713725}{22694743922483} & \frac{-931785054474996708}{22694743922483} & \frac{799974701053192307}{113473719612415} & 0 & 1 \\ \frac{816784820775}{294394698206806016} & \frac{6675149415753}{294394698206806016} & \frac{-148545520998875}{1177578792827224064} & \frac{675021185821125}{1177578792827224064} & \frac{-779956749745173}{294394698206806016} & \frac{6268503501535275}{294394698206806016} & \frac{8400581608123449459}{8243051549790568448} & r & \frac{-1385420343021}{8243051549790568448} \\ \frac{654800}{140378331283} & \frac{-5230064}{140378331283} & \frac{28141092}{140378331283} & \frac{-121250500}{140378331283} & \frac{507886960}{140378331283} & \frac{-3191134800}{140378331283} & \frac{-137597358436}{140378331283} & 0 & r - \frac{40335}{140378331283} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= r^9 - r^8 = 0$$

$$r_1 = 1, r_2 = r_3 = r_4 = r_5 = r_6 = r_7 = r_8 = r_9 = 0 < 1$$

Hence, the block method (13) is zero stable and is of order $P = 11$ and hence by Henrici (1962) it is convergent.

3.3 Absolute Stability Region of the Eight-Step Method

The coefficient of the block method (13) expressed in the form

$$A^{(1)}Y_{w+1} = B^{(0)}Y_w + hC^{(1)}F_w + h^2D^{(1)}G_w \tag{20}$$

Where

$$Y_{w+1} = (y_{n+1}, y_{n+2}, y_{n+3}, \dots, y_{n-k-1}, y_{n+k})^T$$

$$Y_w = (y_{n-k+1}, y_{n-k+2}, y_{n-k+3}, \dots, y_{n-1}, y_n)^T$$

$$F_w = (f_{n+1}, f_{n+2}, y_{n+3}, \dots, f_{n-k-1}, f_{n+k})^T$$

For $w = 0, \dots$ and $n = 0, k, \dots, N - k$.

Applying the test problem

$$y' = \lambda y, \lambda < 0 \quad \text{to yield}$$

$$Y_{w+1} = D(z)Y_w, z = \lambda h$$

$$\text{Where the matrix } D(z) = (r(A - Cz - D1z^2) - B) \tag{21}$$

The matrix $D(z)$ has eigenvalues $\{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \dots, \lambda_k\} = \{0, 0, 0, \dots, \lambda_k\}$

Where the dominant eigenvalue λ_k is the stability function $R(z): \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ which is the rational function with real coefficients.

Figure 1. Region of absolute stability of newly constructed method for k=8

4. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENT

The Solution curves of stiff system plotted were compared with those of MATLAB ODE solver Ode 23.

Problem 1

$$y_1' = 0.01y_1 - y_2 + y_3$$

$$y_2' = y_1 - 100.005y_2 + 99.995y_3$$

$$y_3' = 2y_1 + 99.995y_2 - 100.005y_3$$

Exact $y_1(x) = e^{-0.01x}(\cos 2x + \sin 2x)$

$$y_2(x) = e^{-0.01x}(\cos 2x + \sin 2x) + e^{-200x}$$

$$y_3(x) = e^{-0.01x}(\cos 2x + \sin 2x) - e^{-200x}$$

$$y_1(0) = 1$$

$$y_2(0) = 1$$

$$y_3(0) = 1$$

with $h = 0.1$

Figure 2: Solution Curve of Problem 1 Solved with eight-step

Problem 2

Robertson's Equations

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_1' &= -0.04y_1 + 10000y_2y_3 & y_1(0) &= 1 \\
 y_2' &= 0.04y_1 - 10000y_2y_3 - 30000000y_2^2 & y_2(0) &= 0 \\
 y_3' &= 30000000y_2^2 & y_3(0) &= 0 \\
 & & 0 \leq x \leq 70 & \text{ and } h = 0.1
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3: Solution Curve of Problem 2 Solved with eight-step

5. CONCLUSION

In this research, the uniform order eleven of eight-step hybrid block backward differentiation formulae for the solution of stiff ordinary differential equations was proposed and the scheme with one off-step point were analyzed and to be consistent and zero-stable and convergence. The newly constructed was tested on both linear and nonlinear stiff systems and the results obtained performed favorably compared to exact and ODE23 Solver.

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